

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE TYPES OF MEANING OF WORDS IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract: *This article discusses the relationship between the meaning types of words in English and the semantic features of phraseology.*

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Words are combined into thematic groups according to the fact that they reflect an event, object, action, symbol, etc. in real existence. However, the criteria for combining words into a lexical-semantic group can be different. Words are divided into homonyms, antonyms, synonyms according to their form, meaning and content. These differ from each other in terms of pronunciation and spelling. Words that are pronounced or written in the same way and have different meanings are called homonyms. Greek homog means "the same", "onyma" means "name". Homonyms are divided into the following types:

- a) True homonyms: horse-animal, horse-name, horse-to throw something, horse-to shoot with a rifle.
- b) Amophones with the same pronunciation and different spelling and lexical meanings: worm-insect, dry-milk food made from yogurt.
- v) Homographs, i.e. words with the same spelling but different meanings and pronunciation: tear-eyes, tear-tear.
- g) Homoform or lexical grammatical homonyms, i.e. words with the same grammatical form but different meanings: light-erug`, light-light. Homonyms also

occur as a result of language changes. For example: piece, piace, peace, weak, week, etc.

Some homonyms are formed as a result of matching the spelling and pronunciation of words from another language to the spelling and pronunciation of words in the native language.

There is a big difference between spelling and pronunciation of words in English. Different crushing words can be pronounced the same in it. For example: knight, night, die, dye. Words that differ in meaning and are pronounced and written the same are called complete homonyms. If the words are only written or pronounced the same, they are called incomplete homonyms. When distinguishing homonyms, it is necessary to take into account their historical origin. For example: to be born (birth of a baby), to be born (birth of fiction). Both are derived from the same root. In the origin of homonyms, the necessary rules of sound changes in the language and semantic shifts are an important source. Homonyms are specific to the language system.

Types and meanings of words are clarified by shortening them. The similarity of word meanings is synonyms, and the opposite is antonyms.

Words grouped with opposite meanings are called antonyms (Greek anti-"opposite" onyma-"name"). Antonyms are divided into lexical and grammatical sets.

Lexical antonyms: good-bad, long-short, white-black, long-short, etc.

Grammatical antonyms: salty-non-salty, sweet-nonsense, busy-unworking.

Antonyms are further divided into the following three types.

Antonyms of gradual and coordinated contrasts: rich-poor, day-night.

Conversion antonyms of opposites: war-peace, husband-wife.

Dichotomous division of concepts: legal-illegal, ataka-contrataka.

Antonyms occur between words that have mutually exclusive meanings. They can have their own synonyms. For example: short (small) - novcha (long).

Synonyms are divided into four types:

Words that can be used interchangeably without affecting the meaning are called absolute synonyms. For example: linguistics-linguistics.

Words that differ in meaning belong to the semantic type of synonyms. For example: brave, brave, fearless, bold.

Synonyms that are used interchangeably in terms of meaning in the speech situation or context are called contextual synonyms. For example: poet, swimmer, writer.

The synonyms expressing emotional expressive feeling in meaning are called stylistic synonyms. For example: yuz, bet, bashara, aft, chehra, turq, nusha, etc.

Sometimes a word from a foreign language is used to express the same meaning as a word in the native language and becomes a synonym. For example: prosecutor-accuser, lawyer-accuser. A set of synonyms in a language is called synonymy.

Another branch of lexicology combined with lexicography is phraseology. It explores two or more compound meanings similar to "raining cats and dogs". Because the whole meaning of this phrase is different from the meaning of one word. Phraseology examines how and why such words are used today, the combinations of these words, and the governing laws. By studying the semantic features of phraseologisms, it was determined that they have phraseological polysemy, phraseological homonymy, phraseological antonymy and phraseological antonymy phenomena. Phraseologisms are especially rich in lexical-semantic synonyms. The phrase "to be in a bad mood", which only means "to be upset", has 9 synonyms in English.

To be down in the month.

To be in a bad temper.

To be in a bad mood.

To be in a low spirit.

To be in the dumps.

To be out of humor.

To be out of sorts.

To be out of spirit.

Phraseology is the study of idioms. There are also idioms in English that are synonymous with each other. For example: Dead to the world - hard as a comb. In this

Out like a light - to fall asleep.

Jonked out - to snort, the phrases are synonymous.

brother didn't go to bed until three in the morning and was still dead to the world.

In this sentence, the phrase "dead to the world" comes together with the past tense form of the verb "to be" and acts as a predicative. Each idiom is also a component.

In conclusion, based on the comments of our linguists about lexical meaning given below, we give the following definition of lexical meaning. The lexical meaning of the language unit (lexical unit) is recognized and accepted by the speaker of this language. The lexical meaning is part of the lexical unit. Accordingly, it is given and explained in universal dictionaries. The lexical meaning is common for the speech of speakers of this language. Lexical meaning appears in the context. Context exaggerates one lexical meaning of a polysemous lexeme and separates it from other lexical meanings. Therefore, the lexical meaning does not arise due to specific connections, but is formed in this context. The context reveals this. The lexical meaning is attached to the lexeme as a lexical unit and becomes stable. Lexical meaning usually serves to name a reality.

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